

Influence of Pyrogallol Chelate Complex of Copper(II) on Potassium Monopersulphate Decomposition and Acrylonitrile Polymerisation in Solution

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Manuscript received 20 December 1985, revised 2 April 1987, accepted 11 August 1987

The catalytic influence of various Cu^{2+} salts and Cu^{2+} /phenols couples on potassium monopersulphate decomposition and vinyl polymerisation of acrylonitrile have been investigated in aqueous medium. From the knowledge of the comparative rate data, CuSO_4 /pyrogallol couple has been chosen for the detailed study of the kinetics of acrylonitrile polymerisation. The polymerisation has been studied at various concentrations of reacting components and over the temperature range $35-50^\circ$. The rate of polymerisation has been found to be,

$$R_p = k[\text{Cu}^{2+}]^{0.2} [\text{PY}]^{0.34} [\text{KHSO}_5]^{1.1} [\text{AN}]^{1.0}$$

From the kinetic results and the spectrophotometrical measurements, the catalytic efficiency of Cu^{2+} /pyrogallol couple on the course of KHSO_5 decomposition and acrylonitrile polymerisation has been examined.

PEROXYGEN compounds like dibenzoyl peroxide, peracetic acid, t-butyl hydroperoxide, cumene hydroperoxide, H_2O_2 , $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, $\text{K}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_8$ etc. have separate identity of their own due to their extensive use and applications as free radical initiators and/or curing agents for polymers. The rate of decomposition of these compounds to free radicals is significantly affected in the presence of some metal salts and metal salt/complexing agent couples leading to facile homolysis of the peroxy linkage and this in turn causes high rate of initiation in vinyl and diene polymerisation. It has therefore become customary that in radical polymerisation involving peroxy initiators, metal salts are often used as the components of the redox pair¹⁻¹⁸. However, no report seems to be available on the use of potassium monopersulphate (KHSO_5) as a free radical initiator except a few preliminary reports by our group¹⁹⁻²⁰. The present communication is concerned with, Cu^{2+} /PY couple catalysed decomposition of KHSO_5 and radical polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The novel aspect of the studies is that metal salts and phenols which are recognised as retarders and/or inhibitors of radical polymerisation change their character when coupled together in solution in appropriate molar ratio.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile was purified as reported earlier¹⁹. A stock solution (0.13 M) of the initiator KHSO_5 prepared in triple-distilled water, was used for all experiments. All other reagents were of AnalaR

grade and were used after purification by standard methods.

The polymerisation reactions for the controlled and tri-component system were carried out as reported earlier²⁴. The precipitated polymers were filtered, washed repeatedly with distilled water and dried to constant weight at 60° . The rate of polymerisation was obtained by gravimetry and the rate of initiator disappearance by cerimetry.

The molecular weights of the purified polymers in DMF were determined in a Ubbelohde type suspended level dilution viscometer at 30° using the relationship²⁷,

$$[\eta] = 3.335 \times 10^{-4} \bar{M}_w^{0.72}$$

Results and Discussion

To explore the possible use of freeradical retarders and/or inhibitors as catalyst in radical polymerisation, acrylonitrile in aqueous solution was polymerised using KHSO_5 as initiator in conjunction with Cu^{2+} -salts and Cu^{2+} /phenol couples. Prior to the detailed kinetic investigations involving the system Cu^{2+} -sulphate/pyrogallol/ KHSO_5 , reference experiments were performed Cu^{2+} /phenols couples failed to initiate the polymerisation of acrylonitrile under identical reaction conditions in absence of KHSO_5 . The results of the comparative polymerisation are recorded in

TABLE 1—RATE OF ACRYLONITRILE POLYMERISATION (R_p) CATALYSED BY VARIOUS Cu^{II} SALTS, PHENOLS AND Cu^{II} /PHENOL COUPLES, INITIATED BY POTASSIUM MONOPERSULPHATE

$[KHSO_5] = 13.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cu^{II}] = 0.02 M$, $[Phenol] = 0.0015 M$, $[AN] = 0.754 M$,
Temp = 50° , Control : $R_p = 1.67 \times 10^{-5} ml^{-1} s^{-1}$

Phenols	$(R_p \times 10^5 \text{ m dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$				Without Cu^{II} -salt
	$CuSO_4$	$Cu(NO_3)_2$	$CuCl_2$	$Cu(OAc)_2$	
Without phenol	2.51	2.33	7.11	12.0	1.67
Phenol	5.67	6.22	1.71	10.3	1.35
<i>o</i> -(Cl)-Phenol	3.39	3.42	5.25	12.0	0.86
<i>p</i> -Cresol	10.1	9.52	5.24	13.6	2.34
<i>o</i> -(NO_2)-phenol	2.53	2.57	1.50	10.3	0.91
<i>p</i> -(NO_2)-phenol	2.87	3.28	5.14	12.6	0.81
Catechol	10.4	12.0	4.87	13.3	3.66
Resorcinol	18.0	16.8	8.97	15.4	9.92
Hydroquinone	14.6	8.5	7.02	14.0	4.67
Salicylaldehyde	8.89	13.4	5.04	13.3	0.81
<i>m</i> -(OH) benzaldehyde	10.5	10.7	6.03	11.8	3.85
Pyrogallol	15.4	15.5	4.91	16.1	9.45
α -Naphthol	9.4	10.6	5.92	14.2	4.89
β -Naphthol	10.0	11.8	5.09	12.5	4.92

Table 1 along with the rate data for non-catalysed process.

The results (Table 1) indicate that the R_p value for the couple catalysis is higher than the sum of the individual R_p values,

$$R_p(PY|Cu^{II}|KHSO_5) > (R_p(KHSO_5) + R_p(Cu^{II}|KHSO_5) + R_p(PY|KHSO_5))$$

The low rate with $CuSO_4$ might be due to weak interaction of the vacant d-orbital of Cu^{II} ion with

bridged peroxy orbital of $KHSO_5$ that generates initiating radicals at a slow rate. This is substantiated from the study of visible spectral pattern (Figs not shown) of $CuSO_4$ and $CuSO_4/KHSO_5$ mixture. Similar observations were noticed by several other workers^{8-10, 13-15} in the transition metal salts catalysed decomposition of hydroperoxides. The high R_p value with Cu^{II}/PY couple may probably be due to high rate of production of initiating radicals generated by the facile homolysis of the initiator in the immediate vicinity of Cu^{II}/PY couple where the internal energy is being transferred to the initiator. The $Cu^{II}/pyrogallol$ chelate complex formation has been proved by Dubey and Mehrotra^{2a}.

Effect of pyrogallol concentration :

Acrylonitrile was polymerised in aqueous medium at various concentrations of pyrogallol (0.0001-0.02 M) at fixed concentrations of $CuSO_4$ (0.02 M), $KHSO_5$ (0.013 M), AN (0.754 M) at 40° . From the results (Fig. not shown), it is clear that the initial rate of polymerisation and maximum conversion increase on increasing the concentration of pyrogallol from 0.0001 to 0.005 M and then decreases. The increase of rate with increasing pyrogallol concentration might be due to resultant increase in concentration of the intermediate Cu^{II}/PY couple which in a geometrical array, forces the initiator to undergo spontaneous decomposition, generating radicals in the immediate vicinity of the inter-linked monomer and thereby increasing the rate. At higher pyrogallol concentration, the depression of rate seems to be reasonable arising from (i) radical trapping by excess pyrogallol through a chain-transfer process, and (ii) interaction with growing polymer radicals, ceasing their growth. The inhibition and retardation of radical polymerisation by pyrogallol has been recognised by us in our previous communication^{2a}.

Fig. 1 Variation of R_p with [Monomer] at various temperatures; $[KHSO_5] = 0.013 M$; $[PY] = 0.005 M$, $[CuSO_4] = 0.0005 M$: (a) $[AN]$ vs $10^5 \times R_p$ at ($\square$) 35° , ($\circ$) 40° and (Δ) 50° , (b) $(2 + \log [AN])$ vs $(6 + \log R_p)$ at ($\bullet$) 40°

Effect of copper sulphate concentration :

Initial rate of polymerisation and maximum conversion increase on increasing the concentration of CuSO_4 from 5×10^{-8} to $0.002 M$, after which the rate remains almost constant upto $0.03 M$ and then decreases (Fig not shown). The increase rate with increasing Cu^{2+} ions between the mentioned ranges may be attributed to increasing Cu^{2+} -PY mole ratio which favours in the formation of an active agent, whose internal energy is transferred to the initiator to undergo spontaneous decomposition to radicals and thereby enhancing the rate. Indicator and Sahani^{17,18} noticed similar rate enhancement in the *t*-butyl hydroperoxide decomposition and vinyl polymerisation, catalysed by Mn^{2+} -acetylacetonate complex of appropriate molar ratio. The depression of rate at higher Cu^{2+} ion concentration beyond $0.002 M$, is a known phenomena where higher valency transition metal ions interact with growing polymer radicals causing premature termination of the rate²⁰.

Effect of initiator concentration :

The initial rate of polymerisation and maximum conversion have been found to increase steadily with increasing the concentration of KHSO_5 (3.22×10^{-3} – $38.7 \times 10^{-3} M$) (Fig. not shown). The progressive enhancement of rate with $[\text{KHSO}_5]$ may be due to the greater availability of the initiator in solution at the conformationally favourable energy transfer site of the Cu^{2+} /PY couple intermediate which on interaction produces highly concentrated initiating radical and thus increasing the rate.

Rate of polymerisation :

With monomer concentration : The rate of polymerisation (R_p) increases with the increase of monomer concentration (0.1508 – $1.055 M$) at fixed concentration of CuSO_4 ($0.0005 M$), KHSO_5 ($0.013 M$) and PY ($0.005 M$). Plots of R_p vs $[\text{AN}]$ are linear exhibiting intercept on the rate-axis with unity slope (Fig 1). This indicates a first order dependence of the rate on monomer concentration. Increase of temperature from 35 to 50° has no significant effect on the rate. The required activation energy for facile decomposition of the initiator may be a contribution of Cu^{2+} /PY complex through collisional deactivation of the latter.

With KHSO_5 concentration. The polymerisation rate (R_p) increases on increasing concentration of the initiator (3.22×10^{-3} – $35.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) at fixed concentrations of CuSO_4 ($0.0005 M$), PY ($0.005 M$) and AN ($0.754 M$). The R_p vs $[\text{KHSO}_5]$ plots are linear and pass through the origin and $\log R_p$ vs $\log [\text{KHSO}_5]$ (Fig. not shown) with overall slope of 1.1, describe the process to be first order dependent on KHSO_5 concentration. This, however, deviates from normal half-order dependence of rate on initiator concentration in conventional

free radical polymerisation. Further, that R_p is independent of temperature may be due to similar phenomena as described in the case of monomer variation.

With pyrogallol concentration : R_p steadily increases with pyrogallol concentration from 5×10^{-3} to $3 \times 10^{-2} M$ after which a rapid depletion is noticed (Fig. not shown). Further, the plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [\text{PY}]$ within the cited range is linear with slope of 0.34. The enhancement and depression of R_p are due to the same effect as described earlier.

With copper sulphate concentration : R_p increases with increasing concentration of Cu^{2+} -sulphate (2.5×10^{-7} – $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$) and thereafter decreases. Plot of $\log R_p$ vs $\log [\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ is linear (Fig. not shown) with slope of 0.2. The enhancement of rate with $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ may be attributed to the increase in the rate of primary radical formation caused by interference of Cu^{2+} /PY couple. The increase of temperature has no effect on the rate.

With added acid : With increase in the concentration of H_2SO_4 in the reaction mixture, the R_p value remains unaltered indicating that the polymerisation process is pH-independent.

Polymerisation mechanism :

Polymerisation of acrylonitrile initiated by the system Cu^{2+} /PY/ KHSO_5 is characteristic of heterogeneous polymerisation. From the proportionalities obtained between measured parameters and variables, the rate of polymerisation has been found to be

$$R_p = [\text{AN}]^{1.0} [\text{KHSO}_5]^{1.1} [\text{Cu}^{2+}]^{0.2} [\text{PY}]^{0.3}$$

The proportionalities of the rate to the first power of initiator concentration deviates the reactions from a simple path involving decomposition of KHSO_5 to generate initiating radicals followed by initiation of polymerisation; rather a complex initiation mechanism is involved.

The mode of initiator decomposition, chain initiation and termination may take the following course which has some similarity to that reported by Reddy *et al*²¹ where the pyrogallol coupled to Cu^{2+} may suffer oxidation.

Radical formation :

Since the radicals produced in step (1) are consumed during subsequent step (3), the chain initiation is considered to be caused by radicals generated in step (5).

Chain initiation :

Propagation :

⋮

Termination :

- (a) Mutual, $\text{M}_n\cdot + \text{M}_m\cdot \xrightarrow{k_4} \text{Polymer}$
 (b) By Cu^{II} or Cu^{II} -complex

$$\frac{d[\text{R}\cdot]}{dt} = k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4 k_5 [\text{HSO}_5^-]^2 [\text{Cu}^{II}] [\text{PY}] - k_4 [\text{M}] [\text{R}\cdot] = 0$$

$$[\text{R}\cdot] = \frac{k_1 [\text{HSO}_5^-]^2 [\text{Cu}^{II}] [\text{PY}]}{k_4 [\text{M}]}$$

where, $k = k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4 k_5$.

Assuming mutual termination we have,

$$[\text{M}_n\cdot] = \left(\frac{k}{k_t}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{HSO}_5^-] [\text{Cu}^{II}]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{PY}]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$R_p = k_p [\text{M}] [\text{M}_n\cdot]$$

$$R_p = \left(\frac{k}{k_t}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} k_p [\text{HSO}_5^-] [\text{M}] [\text{Cu}^{II}]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{PY}]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The derived rate and the experimental rate are almost same with slight deviation in $[\text{Cu}^{II}]$ and $[\text{PY}]$, which may be attributed to side-reactions,

e.g. complex formation oxidative disproportionation, radical dimerisation, chain termination by Cu^{II} etc.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly thankful to the Extramural Research, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support. The authors extend their gratitude to Prof. Y. Ikada, Research Center for Medical Polymers and Biomaterials, Kyoto University, Japan, for valuable suggestions.

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